

Professional Transition Among the Savitha (Barber) Community: Socio-Economic and Occupational Shifts

(With Reference to Ballari District)

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Abstract : The Savitha community traditionally engaged in barbering. This community has, however undergone much professional changes owing to modernization, changed social perceptions, and economic difficulties. The research assesses factors propelling the professional changes, the socio-economic consequences, and how the occupation structure is transforming in Ballari District. By utilizing a mixed method, it emerged that out of 100 respondents, the motivating factors are changes in social status and pressure from family in order to shift career. While many respondents are of the view that their social status has improved, most respondents are experiencing financial dissatisfaction and limited career growth. Thus, there is a need for skill development programs and policy interventions to support the community's successful adaptation to modern professions.

IndexTerms - Savitha community, barbering, professional transition, socio-economic impact, modernization, career shift, social status, financial management, skill development, policy intervention.

INTRODUCTION

The Savitha community has been called by the traditional name of the Barber community and has been categorized under the occupational group of India. They primarily belong to the states of Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Tamil Nadu. Throughout their history, the Savithas have been recognized with the skills of hair cutting, shaving, and grooming and are an essential part of people's lives and of ritual ceremonies as well. Traditionally, people would turn to them with many of their private matters in mind. Known by various regional names such as Nayanaja Kshatriya, Nhavi, and Mangala, their occupation was hereditary and deeply embedded in the social fabric. However, modernization and the rise of advanced hairstyling techniques have transformed the profession into a more inclusive, skill-based industry, breaking away from traditional caste barriers. Nevertheless, this community still undergoes socio-economic challenges such as a lack of education, economic disparities, and adjustment to a swiftly changing professional life. "Professional Transition Among the Savitha (Barber) Community: Socio-Economic and Occupational Shifts" is the title given to this study that aims to learn about the community in its trajectory of transition with special emphasis on the socio-economic impacts of such transition and changes in the nature of their occupation. By examining these aspects, the study will try to give insights into the resilience and adaptability of the Savitha community while emphasizing the need for inclusive policies and support systems that would facilitate their successful transition in a modernized world.

Literature Review

The studies on barber communities in India reflect a consistent narrative of transition and struggle. For example, in exploring the Savitha-Samaj, Riyanka Kaushik (2023) outlines historical roles for barbers: haircutting, matchmaking, and basic medical practices and contrasts this trajectory with that of European barber-surgeons, who became formal medical practitioners. Manohara et al. (2023) emphasize the case of Udupi Taluk by noting the shift from caste-based to modern skill-based practices while persistently challenging problems such as low income, social security, and limited training opportunities. The study recommends the following: development of skills, provision of subsidies from the government, and eradication of stigma. Govindappa and Gururaja (2017) also discuss hairdressing saloons in Davanagere, where the sector depends on informal networks, faces competition and lack of credit, and has opportunities for growth through skill development and supportive policies. Tapas Pal (2010) contributes to this discussion by underlining the socio-economic marginalization of barbers in Bolpur, which requires broader measures like barber associations, OBC certificates, and economic diversification. All together, these studies indicate the importance of targeted interventions, modernization, and inclusion for the empowerment of barber communities and their incorporation into the wider socio-economic scheme.

Statement of the Problem

The Savitha community, which has traditionally been associated with barbering, is experiencing significant professional transitions. Such a shift raises critical questions about the factors driving these changes and their broader implications. Key areas of inquiry include understanding the motivations behind leaving traditional occupations, the role of education in shaping new career paths, and the socio-economic consequences of such transitions. Besides, it is necessary to examine the impact of social perceptions on occupational choices and mobility within the community and how such career changes influence the socio-economic status of the individuals. To this end, this study aims to provide an all-rounded understanding of the dynamics of professional transition in the Savitha community and its implications for individual and collective socio-economic well-being.

Research Objectives:

1. To analyze the factors driving professional transition in the Savitha community.
2. To assess the socio-economic impact of career shifts.
3. To explore the influence of social perceptions on occupational choices.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This research is of mixed-methods type, employing qualitative and quantitative analysis to understand the professional transformation of the Savitha community in a holistic manner. The qualitative part will delve into individual stories, social forces, and cultural aspects, while the quantitative method will give statistical data regarding trends, economic effects, and the extent of career transformations.

Data Collection

• **Primary Data:** Primary data will be gathered through interviews and surveys of members of the Savitha community in the Ballari District.

→ Interviews will be taken from a sample of members of the Savitha community who have experienced a professional transformation.

→ Surveys will collect information from a large sample to study patterns of career transitions and socio-economic transformations.

• **Secondary Data:** Secondary data will be gathered from academic studies of the Savitha community, caste-based professions, and the effects of socio-economic transitions.

→ Academic studies will give context to the findings in light of earlier research on caste-based professions and career transitions.

Sampling Method

Purposive sampling will be used to choose members of the Savitha community in Ballari District who have undergone or are undergoing a career change. The sampling technique will be employed to collect diversified views, e.g., those who have shifted to other careers, i.e., government service, entrepreneurship, or daily wages.

Data Analysis

Qualitative Data: Thematic analysis will be employed to identify recurring themes and patterns in interview responses and case studies. This will assist in the identification of underlying factors driving career change, social factors, and personal reasons for change.

Quantitative Data: Statistical analysis, including frequency analysis, cross-tabulation, and correlation analysis, will be employed to analyze survey responses. This will enable the identification of major trends and measurement of socio-economic effects of professional change in the community.

Data Analysis

Data collected from 100 respondents were examined to determine factors that affect career change among barbers, including demographic factors, reasons for career change, change in income, financial satisfaction, and attitudes towards the barber profession. Descriptive statistics and inferential tests were employed to examine the data, and the findings are discussed below.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
Below 18	5	5%
18–30	35	35%
31–45	45	45%
Above 45	15	15%
Total	100	100%

The majority of respondents (45%) were between 31–45 years old, followed by those aged 18–30 years (35%). Only 5% were below 18, and 15% were above 45.

Table 2: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	100	100%
Female	0	0
Total	100	100%

All respondents were male, indicating a significant gender imbalance in the barbering profession in this dataset.

Table 3: Educational Qualifications of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	6	6%
Primary School	41	41%
High School	10	10%
Diploma/ITI	2	2%
Graduate	35	35%
Postgraduate	6	6%
Total	100	100%

Most respondents had a primary school education (41%), followed by graduates (35%). Only 6% had no formal education, and 6% had postgraduate qualifications.

Table 4: Experience

Experience as a Barber	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes (Previously a Barber)	68	68%
No (Not Previously a Barber)	32	32%
Total	100	100%

68% of 100 respondents had previously been barbers, and 32% had not. This indicates that the majority of the sample had experience as a barber.

Table 5: Career Change

Career Change Status	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Changed Career	52	52%
Did Not Change Career	16	16%
Total	100	100%

52% of the respondents had changed careers, and 16% had not. This indicates that the majority of barbers are willing to change careers, potentially due to dissatisfaction with their current career.

Table 6: Reasons for Career Change

(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Social Status or Respect	32	61.5%
Family Pressure	18	34.6%
Availability of Better Opportunities	2	3.8%
Total	52	100%

The most frequent reason for career change was social status or respect, reported by 32 of 52 respondents (61.5%). The second most frequent reason reported was family pressure, by 18 respondents (34.6%). Only 2 respondents (3.8%) mentioned better opportunities, and none mentioned income or job satisfaction.

Table 7: Duration in New Profession

(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)

Duration (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
0–1 year	3	5.8%
1–3 years	13	25%
3–5 years	23	44.2%
More than 5 years	13	25%
Total	52	100%

Most respondents had been in their new profession for 3–5 years (23%), followed by 1–3 years (13%) and more than 5 years (13%). Only 3% had been in their new profession for less than a year.

Table 8: Income Change After Career Transition

(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)

Income Change	Frequency	Percentage
Decreased	38	73.1%
Stayed the Same	11	21.2%
Increased	3	5.8%
Total	52	100%

A significant majority of respondents (73.1%, n = 38) reported a decrease in income after transitioning to a new profession, while only 5.8% (n = 3) reported an increase. 21.2% (n = 11) said their income stayed the same.

Table 9: Financial Satisfaction in New Profession*(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)*

Financial Satisfaction	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Less Satisfied	41	78.8%
More Satisfied	11	21.2%
Total	52	100%

Out Of 52 participants, 41 (78.8%) reported being less financially satisfied in their new profession, and only 11 (21.2%) reported being more satisfied.

Table 10: Career Growth in New Profession*(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)*

Career Growth Perception	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
No Greater Opportunity	43	82.7%
Greater Opportunity	9	17.3%
Total	52	100%

82.7% (n = 43) of the respondents reported that the new occupation provided no greater opportunity for career growth than barbering, and only 17.3% (n = 9) reported that it did.

Table 11: Social Status Change After Career Transition*(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)*

Social Status Change	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Improved	39	75%
Remained the Same	13	25%
Decreased	0	0%
Total	52	100%

75% (n = 39) of the respondents reported social status improved on transition, and 25% (n = 13) reported it remained the same. None reported a decrease in status.

Table 12: Societal Perception of Barbering

Societal Perception	Frequency	Percentage
Low-status	51	98.1%
Neutral	1	1.9%
Total	52	100%

98.1% (n = 51) of the respondents reported that society perceives barbering as a low-status occupation, and only 1.9% (n = 1) perceived it as neutral. None perceived it as respectable.

Table 13: Pressure from Family and Close Aides to Leave Barbering*(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)*

Response	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	20	38.5%
No	32	61.5%
Total	52	100%

38.5% of respondents (n = 20) felt pressured to leave barbering, while 61.5% (n = 32) did not.

Table 14: Respect in New Job*(Out of 52 respondents who changed careers)*

Perception of New Profession	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
More Respectable	49	94.2%
Same as Before	3	5.8%
Less Respectable	0	0%
Total	52	100%

94.2% of respondents (n = 49) felt that their new profession was more respectable, while 5.8% (n = 3) saw it as the same as before. None viewed it as less respectable.

Table 15: Social Circle View on New Job

Social Circle Perception	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Somewhat Positive	29	55.8%
Positive	19	36.5%
Negative	4	7.7%
Total	52	100%

55.8% of respondents (n = 29) reported a somewhat positive view from their social circle, while 36.5% (n = 19) reported a positive view. Only 7.7% (n = 4) reported a negative view.

Table 16: Income vs. Satisfaction

Income Change	More Satisfied (%)	Not Satisfied (%)	Total Respondents
Income Decreased	38 (90.5%)	3 (9.5%)	42

Income Increased	7 (63.6%)	4 (36.4%)	11
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Among respondents whose income decreased, 90.5% (n = 38) were more satisfied, while 9.5% (n = 3) were not. Among those whose income increased, 63.6% (n = 7) were more satisfied, while 36.4% (n = 4) were not.

Recommendations

Based on the results, the following policy recommendations are made to address the challenges of barbers and enhance their professional standing:

1. **Improve Social Perception of Barbering:**
 - a. Conduct public awareness campaigns to emphasize the dignity and significance of the barbering profession.
 - b. Partner with media and influencers to present barbering as a respectable and skilled profession.
2. **Improve Financial Incentives:**
 - a. Offer financial assistance or subsidies to barbers to assist them in maintaining their businesses, particularly during economic recession.
3. **Facilitate Career Growth Opportunities:**
 - a. Develop certification programs and advanced training modules to enable barbers to upgrade their skills and seek new career opportunities in the profession.
 - b. Stimulate barbers to diversify their services (e.g., grooming, skincare) to improve income potential and job satisfaction.
4. **Alleviate Pressure to Leave Barbering:**
 - a. Offer training and mentorship programs to assist barbers in managing societal pressures and building confidence in the profession.
 - b. Develop support networks where barbers can exchange experiences and obtain advice from peers.
5. **Enhance Education and Training:**
 - a. Partner with vocational training institutions to offer vocational training programs in barbering, emphasizing both technical skills and business management.
 - b. Offer scholarships or financial assistance for barbers who want to pursue higher education or specialized training.
6. **Improve Social Status:**
 - a. Reward and acknowledge the contributions of barbers with awards and recognition programs at local and national levels.
 - b. Stimulate barbers to engage in community activities and programs to build a favourable public image.
7. **Monitor and Evaluate Policies:**

Develop a monitoring and evaluation system to evaluate the effectiveness of policies to enhance the barbering profession. Gather feedback from barbers regularly to determine emerging issues and modify policies accordingly.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicates that **Social Status** and **Respect** are the greatest motivators for career change among the Savitha (Barber) community, with economic dissatisfaction and restricted career advancement in new careers being important consequences. Social perception of barbering as a low-status occupation also contributes to the pressure to switch to other occupations. It is thus essential that policymakers reconfigure the social image of barbering, improve the economic incentive system, and provide career advancement to facilitate them to attain higher job satisfaction and professional satisfaction. All these will not only improve the well-being of barbers but also overall development and growth of the grooming sector.

REFERENCES

1. Kaushik, P. (2023). Barber-surgeons. Shodh Samagam.
2. Manohara, M., Rajesh, R., Vishalakshi, M., & Ramprasad, S. (2023). Professional changes among the barbers: A study of Udupi Taluk. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, 10(6), i810. <https://www.jetir.org>
3. Govindappa, G.T., & Gururaja, B.L. (2024). Service sector MSEs: Hair-dressing saloons in Davangere. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 44(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0970846420170104>
4. Pal, T. (2010). Social area analysis of barber and changes: A micro-level study of Bolpur town, West Bengal, India. *The Journal of International Social Research*, 3(14)
5. <https://www.ncbc.nic.in/Writereaddata/cl/karnataka.pdf>